

COMPARISON OF SENTENCE STRUCTURES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation. *The comparison of sentence structures in English and Uzbek languages plays a pivotal role to understand grammatical systems of the two languages. During the comparison two type of structure, the locations of subject, verb and objects will be more precise in both languages and this adds a significant share to the language typology subject. In this article, the linguistic comparison, which is the comparison of the given different structures of two languages, is performed. This comparison also includes related examples to this topic and detailed explanation with necessary terms.*

Key words: *Verb, Subject, Comparison, Comperative*

Annotatsiya. *Ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi jumla tuzilmalarini taqqoslash ikki tilning grammatik tizimini tushunishda muhim rol o'ynaydi. Ikki turdagi tuzilmalarni taqqoslashda sub'ekt, fe'l va ob'ektlarning joylashuvi ikkala tilda ham aniqroq bo'ladi va bu sub'ektning til tipologiyasiga sezilarli ulush qo'shadi. Ushbu maqolada ikki tilning berilgan turli tuzilmalarini taqqoslash bo'lgan lingvistik taqqoslash amalga oshiriladi. Ushbu taqqoslash, shuningdek, ushbu mavzuga tegishli misollarni va zarur shartlar bilan batafsil tushuntirishni o'z ichiga oladi.*

Tayanch so'zlar: *Fe'l, Subyekt, taqqoslash, taqqoslovchi*

Аннотация. *Сравнение структур предложений английского и узбекского языков играет решающую роль для понимания грамматических систем двух языков. При сравнении двух типов структуры расположение подлежащего, глагола и дополнения будет более точным в обоих языках, что добавляет существенную долю субъекту языковой типологии. В данной статье проводится лингвистическое сравнение, которое представляет собой сопоставление заданных различных структур двух языков. Это сравнение также включает примеры, относящиеся к этой теме, и подробное объяснение с необходимыми терминами.*

Ключевые слова: *Глагол, Подлежащее, Сравнение, Сравнительное сравнение.*

In grammar section, comprehending the importance of subjects, verbs, and objects reinforces dynamics and accuracy of language usage. because people need to know what role a word is doing in the sentence to keep grammatical accuracy. However, in many cases, students learn languages via direct and communicative methods and because of that, they encounter some challenges on grammar part. It would be good if language learners study sentence structures of their native languages before trying to learn a totally different language. This is because, learning with comparing sentence structures of two languages is more effective and below, some example on comparisons of sentence structures are conducted.

Basic Sentence Structure

In English, the sentence structure is **Subject+Verb+Object** (SVO) For example:

“I eat an apple”

In Uzbek language, **Subject+Object+Verb** (SOV) word order, which is typical of Turkic languages. For example:

"Men olma yeyman." (Literal translation: "I an apple eat.")

Sentences in compared languages may be also composite.¹ In general composite sentences in compared languages are divided into compound, complex and compound-complex.¹ For example:

*"The Darkness was thinning, but the street was still dimly lighting."*¹

*"Osmonga bulut chiqdi va yomg'ir yog'a boshladi."*¹

In Uzbek language, time comes first. While in English, it is at the end.

In English: *"We'll eat dinner **at five**."*²

In Uzbek: *"Biz kechki ovqatni **saot beshda** yeymiz"*

¹ Rasulova M.I., Shukurova Z.I. "COMPARATIVE TYPOLOGY OF ENGLISH, UZBEK AND RUSSIAN" LANGUAGES. T, 2017: Uzbekistan State World Languages University p 121

² Matt Ellis. "Sentence Structure: Learn the Rules for Every Sentence Type" www.Grammarly.com 2023

To sum up, the sentence structures of the given two languages, English and Uzbek, are different. Especially, this is more obvious at complex sentences. This is why, comparison adds a huge share to linguistic science.

REFERENCES

1. Rasulova M.I., Shukurova Z.I. "COMPARATIVE TYPOLOGY OF ENGLISH, UZBEK AND RUSSIAN" LANGUAGES. T, 2017: Uzbekistan State World Languages University 260 p
2. Matt Ellis. "Sentence Structure: Learn the Rules for Every Sentence Type" www.Grammarly.com 2023